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MULTI-VECTOR PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO IMPROVING COLLABORATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. The authors of the publication analyze the essence of collaborative learning based on foreign sources. It is noted that collaborative learning allows developing students' responsibility for joint activities and contributes to the formation of collective intelligence. Collaborative learning is most effective when students work on creating a common project. The services that allow organizing collaborative e-learning are listed (Google Drive, Podio, Show Document, Open Study, Kidblog, Padlet, etc.).

Keywords: sociality, social skills, collaborative learning, cooperation, teamwork.

INTRODUCTION

The cardinal changes that have affected all spheres of modern human activity are caused by technological breakthroughs in the field of artificial intelligence, robotics, the Internet of Things, nanotechnology, biotechnology, materials science, energy accumulation and storage, etc. Modern people study, work, communicate, and express themselves in a new virtual-real space. Sociologists note that the modern generation of young people lives in online sociality, the main means of communication in which is "public intimacy". The new sociality brings with it not only new opportunities for personal development (self-presentation, self-realization, etc.), but also new risks associated with the lack of social interaction skills. Therefore, one of the areas of modern pedagogical practice is the problem of developing social skills in students through joint activities.

MAIN PART

Social skills are most effectively formed and developed in collaboration, when two or more people interact. During joint work, each person has certain personal goals, but to achieve a common goal, it is necessary to compromise. In this publication, we will consider collaborative learning (from the verb "collaborate") - learning in which people work with each other to achieve one goal, but not necessarily to complete one task. In collaborative learning, responsibility is constantly divided between all participants and their actions

affect the final results. Collaboration is characterized as a philosophy of interaction between people working together to obtain a specific product or goal [1], organized cooperation [2].

The phenomenon of "collaborative learning" in Russian pedagogy has not yet been sufficiently studied. Most authors consider the possibilities of collaborative learning in a web environment [3], in the conditions of the information and educational environment of a university [4], in an electronic network environment [2], based on web 2.0 technologies [3] and metadata [2], in social networks [1]. Collaboration is actively used in business processes and international scientific programs [3], etc. Bruffee's ideas about collaborative learning are based on the statements of Thomas Kuhn that knowledge belongs to a certain social group. Since learning is a social construction of knowledge, it is necessary to rely on group work methods. Bruffee believes that knowledge is something that people build together during discussions, reaching an agreement between students and teachers. To achieve this, students must be able to work and listen to others, respecting each person's contribution, synthesizing different points of view. In this case, collaborative learning turns into a joint activity of students and teachers aimed at creating new knowledge, since most of the time students must ask questions, discuss problems and exchange opinions on the material being studied.

Collaborative learning allows developing students' responsibility for joint activities, gaining new knowledge in conditions of interaction with each other and with the teacher.

Foreign authors [3] describe the stages of collaborative learning:

- familiarization - the student gets acquainted with the material being studied in any form (lecture, books, Internet, etc.);
- research - students prepare initial reasoning, express their opinions out loud;
- transformation - students process information for a deeper understanding, the teacher, if necessary, corrects the students' shortcomings and provides additional information;
- presentation - students present their understanding within a group (from 2 people);
- reflection - the student's awareness of the material studied and the experience gained.

The effectiveness of collaborative interaction depends on the conscious goal-setting and motivation for joint work, how deeply the participants are immersed

in achieving the set goals. Therefore, the main task of leaders of collaborative interaction is to assess the progress of the community's activities and support coordination between them and its goals. Analyzing collaborative interaction in digital networks, J. Fraissin [4] noted that "individuals gradually merge with the group, which becomes a single whole", ... the interaction of group members is long-term, and it is the consistency of the team that helps in achieving the final goal, so the group can perform high-quality work. Collaborative work promotes mutual understanding, which allows not only to convey knowledge and experience, but also to promote personal changes. Mutual understanding as a pedagogical phenomenon is a source of personal self-development, a space for deep communication and interrelated self-development of participants in the educational process, a means of open, subtle and most effective pedagogical mutual influence, a factor in enriching pedagogical interaction, the foundation of free, relaxed relations between teacher and student [2].

With regard to the didactic process, oral and written interactions contribute to the best understanding of the educational material, and form the ability to experience social interaction in learning.

Electronic collaborative learning contributes to the formation of collective intelligence, while cyberspace is used as a tool to support collective intellectual activity, allowing for communication between participants in the global educational process. In this format of collaborative learning, the teacher coordinates the work of all participants, provides collective and individual assessment, conducts individual and group consultations, maintains a friendly atmosphere, motivates and creates a "team spirit".

Effective collaborative activity should cover the entire learning process: students should use their knowledge to make joint decisions (content), plan activities (process), and develop fundamentally new solutions (result). Collaboration in e-learning is classified by time, type of communication, and the number of transmitters and receivers involved in completing a common task [3]. The main elements of collaborative e-learning include: a common task, a list of roles, technologies and services, people (with certain competencies), the physical environment, and the social environment. In the practice of collaborative learning, web tools are actively used to complete educational projects [2]: blogs, webinars, mind maps, chats, teleconferences, video conferences, online meetings, instant messages, Internet portals, news groups, social networks, whiteboards.

CONCLUSION

Teachers note the effectiveness of the Google Drive service, which allows for real-time collaboration, provides the ability to demonstrate individual work to a group, collaborate on documents, organize storage available to group members, and the ability to collaborate with other partners. Podio is designed for teamwork, allows for project management, the ability to interact in real time, and track changes made by different users working in the same file. Show Document is an online program that offers a wide range of collaboration tools for free. Open Study is a bulletin board that allows for the creation of online research groups. Kidblog allows for the creation of blogs and creative assignments in the humanities, Padlet allows for the creation of a virtual wall for collaborative discussion. As we can see, many tools have been developed to organize collaborative e-learning.

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